

Burnout of Secondary School Teachers in Relation to Their Job Satisfaction

Dr. Sarmistha Choudhury¹, Sohail M Sangma²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Education University of Science and Technology Meghalaya

²PG Student, Department of Education University of Science and Technology Meghalaya

Abstract- Teaching at the secondary school level demands not only subject expertise but also sustained emotional engagement and adaptability in the face of diverse classroom challenges. These demands, coupled with institutional pressures, can contribute to a state of professional burnout is a phenomenon characterized by emotional weariness, depersonalization, and diminished sense of personal achievement. Such experiences may, in turn, influence how teachers perceive their work, shaping their overall sense of job satisfaction. This study investigates the rate of burnout among secondary school educators and explores patterns in their levels of job satisfaction. Further, it investigates how these two variables interact, providing insight into whether and to what extent burnout impacts teachers' professional contentment. Using standardized measures — the Teachers' Burnout Scale (TBS) by Prof. Madhu Gupta & Ms. Surekha Rani (2011) and the Teachers' Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (TJSQ) by Dr. Amar Singh & Dr. T.R. Sharma (1999) — data were collected from a representative sample of educators. The analysis offers a profound understanding of the emotional and motivational dynamics within profession of teaching with implications for policy and practice aimed at enhancing teacher well-being and effectiveness.

Keywords: Teachers' Burnout, Teachers' Job Satisfaction & Secondary School.

I. INTRODUCTION

Burnout is a poor psychological state brought on by stress at work. It relates to the emotions felt by those whose work frequently exposes them to social settings that are emotionally intense. Teachers are among those in helping professions who are exposed to this occupational hazard. Burnout can be thought of as the quenching of a candle or a fire; if it is not given enough resources, it will eventually go out (SchauFiel et al. 2009).

Freudenberger's (1974) was the first to identify burnout, which is characterized by emotions of weakness and tiredness brought on by excessive demands placed on one's energies without enough compensation. Burnout, according to some experts, is psychological disengagement from one's job (Maslach, 1976). Those who engage with others in some form are particularly vulnerable to burnout, which is explained as "a syndrome of Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization, and Reduced Accomplishment" (Leiter & Maslach, 1998). Block (1978).

In secondary schools, teacher burnout is a prevalent problem that can negatively attest both educators and learners. Mismatch between the demands and resources of teaching frequently leads to burnout. Teachers that are burned out may show signs of lack of motivation, decreased involvement with students and a lack of passion which impacts absenteeism, lack of commitment and subpar work performance. Additionally, it may have an impact on classroom management, resulting in cynicism, impatience, and student punishment. Students may find it challenging to learn and reach their academic potential in such a poor learning atmosphere. A teacher's job satisfaction may suffer as a result of burnout, a poor psychological reaction to stress at work. Chronic fatigue brought on by burnout can negatively affect teacher's personal and professional life.

Causes and Effects: Burnout effect can be associated with the statement of problems as typical reasons under the following sub heads:

- **Overwork:** Having too much to do all the time and not enough time to rest. Lack of control: Feeling helpless or incapable of influencing choices that have an impact on your job.

Uncertainty regarding your role duties or expectations at work is known as unclear job expectations. Work that is monotonous or uninteresting; repetitive duties without of variation or purpose. Conflicts at work a lack of support, or toxic leadership are examples of dysfunctional work environments. Overcommitting oneself to work at the expense of one's personal life is known as work life imbalance.

- **Individual considerations:** Perfectionism is the tendency to hold oneself to excessively high standards and to be extremely critical of one. Burnout can have a profound effect on a student's life by lowering their quality of education they receive impeding their engagement in the learning process, and possibly harming their perception of school in general, which lowers motivation and academic performance. A teacher who is experiencing burnout may find it difficult to foster a supportive learning environment, offer sufficient assistance, and uphold positive all relationship with students all of which can have an adverse effect on students' academic progress and general well.

In the past decade, burnout syndrome has emerged as a prominent mental health issue in contemporary countries. In a word that faces major socioeconomic challenges, people experience ever – increasing pressure in their daily lives particularly at the workplace. As a consequence, managers, employees and workers in a variety of sectors around the world suffer from work related stress, fatigue and exhaustion and the most prominent signs of which are often referred to as burnout syndrome.

The prevalence of burnout is estimated to be above 10% by even more cautions and conservative scientific studies; for instance, 13.7% of Dutch working people are reported to have burnout (2003). These results imply that burnout is a significant issue in today's culture.

Burnout is "characterized by emotional exhaustion, and negative attitudes and feelings toward one's co-

workers and job role," stated by the American Psychological Association.

Wilson, 2011, p. 17. Employees in social services who often engage with others experience burnout, a normal psychological reaction to ongoing job stress. In academia, burnout is still not widely acknowledged as a mental disorder in and of itself, especially in clinical psychology and psychiatry. Researchers have often questioned whether burnout is just "psychobabble" or a useful diagnostic (Kaschka, Korczak, and Broich, 2011; Roberts, 1986).

II. NEEDS AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Burnout of teachers and job satisfaction are crucial areas of study because it directly impacts teachers' physical, emotional and mental health. As well as impacting to the student outcomes and achievement because if the teacher is mentally not healthy than the negative outcomes will come in student learning. So, it is important to know the problems of teacher mental wellbeing because they are part of academic and is related to your learning. A good mental health provides a positive - outcomes to the learner. Teachers, job satisfaction influences their motivation and effectiveness, it consequently impacts how well pupils are taught.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- (a) To identify the job burnout of secondary school teachers.
- (b) To find out the level of job satisfaction among secondary school teachers.
- (c) To study the relationship between burnout and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

HYPOTHESIS

H01. There is no significant relationship between burnout and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- (a) The study is delimited to the teachers who are working in secondary level.
- (b) The study is delimited to only specific area Williamnagar in Meghalaya East Garo Hills

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study falls under the Descriptive Survey Method which is one of the most common and useful method of social science research. It studies the present status of the variables of burnout and job satisfaction of higher secondary teachers to collect relevant information and interprets in what conditions and relationships exist at present. The present study follows the correlational approach design in highlighting the major correlational objectives.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY: The population of the present study comprises of all teachers total number of teachers working in secondary school in Williamnagar East Garo Hills. The universe of the present study constitutes all the teachers (Male and Female) belonging to the secondary schools in Williamnagar East Garo Hills. There are total 15 secondary schools in that area and a total number of 246 teachers are working in the said schools.

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

In this study out of 15 secondary schools 7 schools were selected by using simple random sampling method. The teacher participants were selected by using stratified random sampling from 7 schools of Williamnagar Meghalaya. From every school 10 teachers were selected – among them 5 male and 5 female. Thus, total group is consisted of 35 male and 35 female teachers. The selected sample ensures a diverse representation of teachers’ true feelings and

emotions related to burnout and job satisfaction which allowing for a comprehensive analysis.

TOOLS OF THE STUDY

1. Teachers’ Burnout Scale (TBS), Prof. Madhu Gupta & Ms. Surekha Rani, 2011

The Teacher Burnout Scale (TBS) The scale usually involves a series of questions where teachers rate their feelings on a scale, such as how often they feel emotionally drained, detached from students, or less competent in their teaching role. This helps to gauge the intensity and impact of burnout on the teacher's well-being and job satisfaction.

2. Teachers’ Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (TJSQ), Dr. Amar Singh & Dr. T.R. Sharma, 1999.

The level to which workers are happy with their jobs is known as job satisfaction. It conveys the degree of congruence between one's expectations of the employment and the benefits it offers. An individual or a group may be referred to as having job satisfaction.

VARIABLES

Figure 1.1 Types of variables

IV. ANALYSE THE INTERPRETATION DATA

OBJECTIVE 1. To identifies the job burnout of secondary school teachers.

Table 1.1: Showing the Level of Burnout of Secondary School Teachers

Level of Burnout	Grade	Frequency	Percentage
1. Extremely High Level of Burnout	A	0	0
2. High Level of Burnout	B	10	14.28%
3. Above Average Level of Burnout	C	9	12.85%
4. Average Level of Burnout	D	7	10%
5. Below Average Level of Burnout	E	12	17.14%
6. Low level of Burnout	F	21	30%
7. Extremely Low Level of Burnout.	G	11	15.71%
Total		70	100%

Figure 1.2 Level of Burnout of Secondary School Teachers

In the table 1.1 and figure 1.2, it has been shows that the burnout levels among secondary school teachers, none of the teachers experienced an

extremely high level of burnout, while 10 teachers (14.28%) reported a high level and 9 teachers (12.85%) had an above average level of burnout. Seven teachers (10%) fell into the average burnout category, whereas 12 teachers (17.14%) reported below average burnout. The largest group, 21 teachers (30%) experienced a low level of burnout, followed by 11 teachers (15.71%) with an extremely low level. Overall, while 44 teachers (62.85%) low or below average burnout, indicating generally manageable stress level, 19 teachers (27.13%) were in the high or above average burnout range, highlighting a need for targeted support measures.

OBJECTIVE 2: To find out the level of job satisfaction among secondary school teachers.

Table 1.2: Showing the level of Job Satisfaction among Secondary School teachers.

Level of Teacher’s Job Satisfaction	Grade	Frequency	Percentage
1. Extremely Satisfied	A	6	8.57%
2. Highly Satisfied	B	9	12.85%
3. Above average Satisfied	C	21	30%
4. Average/Moderate Satisfied	D	5	7.14%
5. Below Average Satisfied	E	3	4.2%
6. Dis4satisfaction	F	13	18.57%
7. Extremely Dissatisfaction	G	13	18.57%
Total		70	100%

Figure 1.3 Level of Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers

From the table 1.2 and figure1.3, shows that the majority of teachers (30%) reported being above average satisfied with their jobs, followed by high dissatisfaction and extreme dissatisfaction, each reported by 18.57% of respondents. Only a small proportion (8.57%) was extremely satisfied, while high satisfaction was noted by 12.85% and average/moderate satisfaction by 7.14%. Below average satisfaction was the least reported category at 4.2%. Overall, while a significant number of teachers express satisfaction—especially at above-average levels—there is a notable proportion (over 40%) who are dissatisfied to varying degrees,

indicating a need for institutional measures to address the factors contributing to dissatisfaction.

HYPOTHESIS H01. There is no significant relationship between burnout and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

OBJECTIVE 3: To study the relationship between burnout and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

1.3 Table showing the relationship between the burnout and job satisfaction

Level of Burnout	Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction						
	Extremely Satisfied	Highly Satisfied	Above Average Satisfied	Average / Moderate Satisfied	Below Average Satisfied	Dissatisfaction	Extremely Dissatisfaction
1. Extremely High level of Burnout				1		4	10
2. High level of Burnout				2	1	2	9
3. Above Average level of Burnout			10	7		2	
4. Average level of Burnout			1	2	1		
5. Below Average level of Burnout			2		1	2	
6. Low level of Burnout		3	2	3			
7. Extremely Low level of Burnout	3	1				1	

Figure 1.4 Relationship between the burnout and job satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers

From the table no. 1.3 and figure no. 1.4 it has been revealed that out of the total 70 teachers surveyed, 19 teachers (27.1%) reported an Above Average Burnout level, with the highest proportion within this group being Above Average Satisfied (14.3%) and Highly Satisfied (10.0%). 15 teachers (21.4%) experienced Extremely High Burnout, where Dissatisfaction was the dominant response (14.3%), followed by Below Average Satisfaction (5.7%) and Above Average Satisfaction (1.4%). 14 teachers

(20.0%) reported High Burnout, with a substantial percentage expressing Dissatisfaction (12.9%), while Below Average Satisfaction (2.9%) and Above Average Satisfaction (2.9%) were less common. Average Burnout was observed in 4 teachers (5.7%), with responses split between Above Average Satisfaction (1.4%), Average Satisfaction (2.9%), and Below Average Satisfaction (1.4%). 5 teachers (7.1%) had Below Average Burnout, most of whom were Above Average Satisfied (2.9%) or Dissatisfied (2.9%). Low Burnout was reported by 8 teachers (11.4%), where Highly Satisfied (4.3%), Above Average Satisfied (2.9%), and Average Satisfaction (4.3%) were prominent. The smallest group, 5 teachers (7.1%), experienced Extremely Low Burnout, with notable proportions being Extremely Satisfied (4.3%), Highly Satisfied (1.4%), and Extremely Dissatisfied (1.4%).

H01. There is no significant relationship between burnout and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

To prove the null hypothesis the researcher used the Pearson correlation coefficient between burnout and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

$r = -0.71$

Since the calculated correlation (-0.71) is large in magnitude and negative, it provides strong evidence against the null hypothesis. Thus, the null hypothesis that "there is no significant relationship" can be rejected. Therefore, it can be concluded that there exists a significant and negative relationship between burnout and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers. Teachers experiencing higher burnout tend to report lower levels of job satisfaction.

V. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- In this study, it has been found that the majority of teachers (62.85%) fall into the low or below average burnout range, indicating a generally healthy work environment for most. However, more than a quarter of the respondents are experiencing above average or high burnout, which may require targeted interventions to prevent escalation. The absence of extreme burnout cases is positive, but continuous monitoring is necessary to maintain these levels.
- The findings reveal that the highest proportion of teachers (30%) reported being above average satisfied with their jobs, followed by an equal share of respondents (18.57% each) expressing dissatisfaction and extreme dissatisfaction. High satisfaction was reported by 12.85% of teachers, while 8.57% were extremely satisfied. A smaller percentage (7.14%) indicated average or moderate satisfaction, and only 4.2% reported below average satisfaction. Overall, while a considerable proportion of teachers experience positive job satisfaction, a significant segment (over 40%) falls within the dissatisfaction categories, highlighting underlying concerns that may require institutional attention.
- The findings suggest a clear inverse relationship between burnout and job satisfaction — higher burnout levels are largely linked with dissatisfaction, while lower burnout levels are more often associated with higher satisfaction ratings.
- Teachers with Extremely High Burnout (21.4%) and High Burnout (20.0%) together make up 41.4% of the sample, and these two categories alone account for 27.2% of all Dissatisfaction cases. This shows a substantial concentration of negative sentiment in the upper burnout range.
- Teachers in Low Burnout (11.4%) and Extremely Low Burnout (7.1%) together account for 12.9% of all Highly Satisfied and Extremely Satisfied ratings, suggesting lower burnout is consistently associated with higher job satisfaction.
- Above Average Burnout (27.1%) shows an interesting split — while a large share are satisfied (Highly Satisfied or Above Average Satisfied: 24.3% combined), there is still a small percentage (2.9%) reporting dissatisfaction. This indicates that mid-range burnout doesn't necessarily guarantee negative outcomes but is a tipping point.
- With only 5.7% of teachers falling into the Average Burnout category, their satisfaction ratings are scattered across Above Average, Average, and Below Average Satisfaction. This suggests that a moderate burnout level doesn't have a fixed satisfaction outcome.
- Only 1 teacher (1.4%) reported Extreme Dissatisfaction, and they belonged to the Extremely Low Burnout category. This outlier could indicate that job dissatisfaction is not always burnout-driven — factors like workplace politics, career goals, or personal reasons may also play a role.
- As burnout level rises, the percentage of teachers in the Extremely Satisfied and Highly Satisfied categories drops sharply. For instance, Extremely Satisfied is 4.3% in Extremely Low Burnout but 0% in Above Average, High, and Extremely High Burnout.
- Above Average Satisfied (25.7%) is the single most common satisfaction level across all burnout categories, appearing most strongly in Above Average Burnout and Low Burnout.

VI. SUGGESTIONS

1. The study's recommendation is to address unresolved issues for further investigation. The researchers' opinions form the basis of the study proposal. The study's recommendation also addresses the research's limitations. Re-evaluating and extending the theory, framework, or model that has been addressed in research is the suggested course of study.
2. The suggestion for this study is to give a preventive measures to job burnout and job satisfaction to help teachers to reduce their stress and depression which they felt unsatisfied with their job which will ultimately impact their mind and result will go to job burnout. So therefore in order to avoid such burnout among teachers' life a daily short mindfulness or breathing exercises is needed to interrupt the stress cycle.
3. To set clear start identify one skill or area to develop each term try to engage in peer observations to gain fresh ideas without heavy time commitments. A strong relation of principal and his cooperation will help the teachers to feel good and a clear happiness of mind.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Teacher burnout is a serious problem that impacts the general efficacy and sustainability of the educational system in addition to the wellbeing of educators. To preserve job satisfaction and avoid burnout, preventive maintenance techniques are crucial. These include encouraging supportive leadership, making sure workloads are realistic, offering chances for professional development, and encouraging work-life balance. Schools can establish healthier workplaces where educators feel appreciated, encouraged, and supported by making proactive investments in these initiatives. In the end, preventing burnout through preventative maintenance is important for students, long term success and the quality of their education, not only for teachers' mental health.

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